

TERRITORIAL ANALYSIS OF THE NATURAL MOVEMENT OF THE POPULATION OF THE ZARAFSHON REGION

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Abstract. The article describes the demographic situation of Zarafshan economic district. In it, the natural movement of the population is divided into small regions. At the same time, the dynamics of the years have been developed.

Key words: demography, birth, death, natural growth, repopulation, region, marriage, migration.

One of the tasks of modern economic and social geography is to study the territorial characteristics of population production, the impact of economic, social and demographic factors affecting them, population forecast. Studying the demographic situation is important in the study of demographic processes and territorial aspects of population regeneration. Demographic processes are of particular importance in the formation of the demographic situation of the region. The main demographic processes include births, deaths, natural reproduction, marriage and divorce. The study of these processes on the scale of our republic and its individual regions is gaining special importance in the coming years.

The demographic potential of the Zarafshan region is quite large. The region is second only to the Fergana region in terms of population in our country. The area of the region is 167.4 thousand square kilometers or 37.3% of the territory of the republic, and the population is 7145.0 thousand people (01.01.2022) or 20% of the population of the republic. The population density of the region is per square meter. 42.7 people per km. The region's population and its density have very large territorial differences. In terms of population, it is 4 times smaller than Samarkand region

(4094.6 thousand people), Navoi region (1050.1 thousand people), Bukhara region (2000.3 thousand people) 2 times smaller. The districts with the lowest population density here in our republic are Tomdi district (0.33 people per sq. km), Uchquduq district (0.74 people per sq. km), and also districts with relatively low population density of Toyloq district (per sq. km. 765.3 people per km.), Samarkand district (618.5 people per sq. km.), there are districts. We can see such regional differences in population in demographic processes.

In 2021, the birth rate in the region is 24.6 (Bukhara region 21.6, Navoi region 24.6, Samarkand region 27.0) per thousand, with large territorial differences in terms of administrative units. According to the territorial differences in the birth rate, we can divide the cities and districts of the region into four groups;

Areas with a very low birth rate (less than 20.0 per thousand): Tomdi district (16.5 per thousand), Bukhara city

Areas with a low birth rate (20.1-25.0 per thousand): Samarkand, Kattakurgan cities, Narpay district (Samarkand region), Kogon city, Olot, Bukhara, Vobkent, Gijduvon, Kogon, Karakol, Peshku, Romiton, Jondor, Shafirikon districts (Bukhara region), Zarafshan, Ghazgon cities, Kyziltepa, Navbahor, Konimekh districts (Navoi region);

Regions with an average birth rate (25.1-30.0 per thousand): Okdarya, Bulung'ur, Jomboy, Kattakurgan, Nurobot, Pastdargom, Pakhtachi, Samarkand districts (Samarkand region), Qarovulbazar district (Bukhara region), Navoi city, Karmana, Nurota, Khatirchi, Uchkuduq districts (Navoi region);

Regions with a high birth rate (above 30.0 per thousand): Ishtikhan, Koshrabot, Poyarik, Toyloq and Urgut districts (Samarkand region).

Death is one of the main processes in the formation of the demographic situation. Factors affecting death depend on two groups, i.e. endogenous and exogenous factors. Endogenous factors are internal factors, which are factors that are changes in the human body. Exogenous factors are external factors that occur under the influence of the external environment. The impact of the second factor on

regional mortality rates is significant. The population of Zarafshan region was 32,785 people, that is, the total death rate was equal to 4.6 per million. Territorial differences in urban and rural districts are clearly visible.

Areas with a very low overall death rate (up to 4.0 per thousand), Pastdargom, Ishtikhan, Urgut districts (Samarkand region), Qarovulbazar, Peshku districts (Bukhara region), Zarafshan city (Navoi region).

Areas with a relatively low overall death rate (up to 4.1-4.5 per thousand), Okdarya, Bulung'ur, Kattakurgan, Pastdargom, Toyloq districts (Samarkand region), Bukhara, Romiton, Jondor, Shafirkon districts (Bukhara region), Ghazgon city, Kyziltepa, Uchkuduq districts (Navoi region).

Regions with an average death rate (up to 4.6-5.0 per thousand) are Koshrabot, Narpay, Poyarik districts (Samarkand region), Olot, Vobkent, Kogon, Karakol districts (Bukhara region), Navbahor, Khatirchi, Tomdi districts (Navoi region).

The regions with a relatively high mortality rate (over 5.1 per thousand) are Samarkand, Kattakurgan cities, Pastdargom, Pakhtachi districts (Samarkand region), Bukhara, Kogon cities, Gijduvon district (Bukhara region), Navoi city, Karmana, Nurota and Kanimekh districts. (Navoi region).

The natural movement of the population is expressed through indicators of natural growth of the population. There are absolute and relative indicators of natural population growth. Regions cannot be compared on the basis of absolute indicators of population, because the population of each region is different, and the number of births and deaths in them depends on the total population. That is why the natural growth rate is used when comparing the population of regions. The absolute number of natural increase in Zarafshan region was 147419 people. 15.7 per thousand of the population have territorial differences by districts;

Family formation is important in population re-establishment. Studying the territorial characteristics and structure of family formation is one of the important tasks of population geography. The formation of the family is closely related to the processes of marriage and divorce. Marriage is a form of relationship between a man

and a woman, which is formed historically, and is maintained in a certain way by the society, in relation to children. Marriage is a social process that has its own evolution and types. Remarriage is performed according to civil laws and regulations and religious traditions. The number of marriages, in turn, has a positive effect on the birth rate.

We can show the following conclusions in the study of demographic processes and their territorial aspects in the Zarafshan region. Demographic processes of the region showed large regional differences in urban and rural districts. The total fertility rate was low in cities and especially in remote districts located in the desert region. Districts located in the valley and mountainous areas were observed to be high. The overall death rate is higher in cities. It was found in the analyzes that the indicators of natural reproduction are high in rural districts, especially in districts located in mountainous areas

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